

TELEHEALTH KNOWLEDGE, AWARENESS, READINESS, AND PROFESSIONAL ANXIETY AMONG HEALTH SERVICES VOCATIONAL SCHOOL STUDENTS

Keywords

Telemedicine,

Telehealth Education,

Occupational Stress,

Vocational School

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to evaluate the knowledge, awareness, and readiness of the vocational school of health services students regarding telehealth applications, as well as their levels of professional anxiety in relation to these factors. This online, cross-sectional study was conducted with 121 health services vocational school students. Sociodemographic characteristics (age, sex, year of study, department, prior exposure to telehealth) were recorded. Two researcher-developed instruments assessed telehealth competencies: the Telehealth Knowledge and Awareness Questionnaire and the Telehealth Readiness Questionnaire. In addition, professional anxiety was measured with the Professional Anxiety Scale for Health Services Students. Second-year students demonstrated significantly higher technological readiness ($p = 0.016$) and overall telehealth readiness ($p = 0.042$) than first-year students. They also reported higher occupational-health anxiety ($p = 0.022$). No other between-year differences were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Correlation analyses showed that greater telehealth readiness was consistently associated with lower anxiety levels. Readiness dimensions were negatively correlated with working-life, occupational-health, and total anxiety scores ($r = -0.19$ to -0.29 , $p < 0.05$). Technological readiness showed the strongest inverse associations, particularly with working-life anxiety ($r = -0.286$, $p < 0.001$) and occupational-health anxiety ($r = -0.259$, $p = 0.002$). Overall telehealth readiness was similarly inversely related to working-life anxiety ($r = -0.232$, $p = 0.010$), occupational-health anxiety ($r = -0.263$, $p = 0.004$), and total anxiety ($r = -0.193$, $p = 0.034$). In contrast, telehealth knowledge and awareness were not significantly associated with anxiety ($p > 0.05$). The findings are expected to provide guidance for the educational arrangements required to facilitate the integration of this student group, across different healthcare disciplines, into digital health services and make a significant contribution to the literature. Overall, structured telehealth education and larger, multicenter, longitudinal studies are needed to better prepare health-care students for telehealth's growing role.

INTRODUCTION

Telehealth, defined as the delivery of healthcare services between individuals or institutions located in geographically separate areas through information and communication technologies, is a widely accepted strategy to meet patients' health needs¹. By reducing distance-related barriers, this approach has the potential to improve the quality of care, particularly for patients living in remote areas or those with chronic conditions². In recent years, especially with the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, the significance of telehealth applications has increased markedly, becoming an integral component of healthcare services³. Telehealth services have become widespread worldwide and have also gained official recognition in Turkey through legal regulations⁴.

There are various studies in the literature examining the knowledge and attitudes of healthcare students toward telehealth. A systematic review reported that medical students generally demonstrated positive attitudes toward telehealth technologies; however, their level of knowledge regarding their use was insufficient, and most had not received any formal training in this field⁵. In a multicenter study conducted in Europe, 82% of students stated that telehealth should be included in the curriculum, yet only 2.7% reported having in-depth knowledge on the subject. This indicates that although students' interest in telehealth is high, their readiness for its practical implementation remains limited⁶.

In Turkey, only a few studies have been conducted in this field, and these have shown that students' knowledge and awareness of telehealth remain limited, with insufficient representation in the curriculum and inadequate preparation for its implementation⁷. However, no study in the literature has been found that directly focuses on students of vocational schools of health services. These

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students—such as physiotherapy technicians, dialysis technicians, and emergency medical technicians—constitute an important part of the healthcare system and will play an active role in telehealth systems in the near future. Determining the knowledge, awareness, readiness, and professional anxiety levels of students in vocational schools of services is essential for both educational planning and digital health policies.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the knowledge, awareness, and readiness of vocational school of health services students regarding telehealth applications, as well as their levels of professional anxiety in relation to these factors. To the best of our knowledge, this is among the first studies at the vocational school level to address these three concepts together.

METHODS

Study Design

This research was conducted as a cross-sectional and descriptive study. Ethical approval was obtained from the Non-Drug and Medical Device Research Ethics Committee of KTO Karatay University under the number 2025/016. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Participants

The study included volunteer students enrolled in vocational schools of health services at various universities. Data were collected through online questionnaires prepared via Google Forms. The survey forms were distributed to students studying in vocational schools of health services across different provinces of Turkey, thereby ensuring participation from diverse regions. Eligible participants were students aged 18 years or older, who provided written informed consent, and who had the cognitive capacity to complete the questionnaire. Exclusion criteria included: students enrolled in other departments or faculties; individuals younger than 18 years; those who filled out the survey incompletely or invalidly; those who did not provide voluntary consent or withdrew from the study during the process; participants with health conditions preventing survey completion; and those who provided misleading responses that could compromise data quality.

Assessment

Sociodemographic information, including students' age,

gender, year of study, department, and whether they had previously heard of the concept of telehealth, was evaluated using a standardized form. In addition, two questionnaires developed by the researchers were used to assess students' levels of knowledge, awareness, and readiness regarding telehealth applications. To determine the level of professional anxiety, the Professional Anxiety Scale for Health Services Students was administered.

The Telehealth Knowledge and Awareness Questionnaire consists of 25 items and is designed on a five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire comprises three sub-dimensions: Telehealth Knowledge Level (10 items), Telehealth Awareness Level (7 items), and Attitudes and Evaluations Toward Telehealth Applications (8 items). The total score ranges from 25 to 125, with higher scores indicating greater readiness.

The Telehealth Readiness Questionnaire is a 25-item instrument designed on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree). It comprises four sub-dimensions: Cognitive Readiness (7 items), Technological Readiness (7 items), Affective Readiness (5 items), and Readiness for Implementation (6 items). The total score ranges from 25 to 125, with higher scores indicating greater readiness. The Professional Anxiety Scale for Health Services Students was used to assess the level of professional anxiety. Developed by Çelebi et al. (8) specifically for health services students, the scale has been validated for reliability and validity⁸. It consists of 30 items across four sub-dimensions: Professional Knowledge, Working Life, Occupational Health, and Communication. Participants are asked to respond to each item on a three-point scale ranging from 1 (Not anxious) to 3 (Anxious). The total score ranges from 30 to 90, with higher scores indicating greater levels of professional anxiety.

Sample Size

Based on findings from similar studies in the literature^{9,10} and methodological considerations, the effect size was assumed to be Cohen's $d = 0.40$ (moderate level). The significance level (α) was set at 5%, and the statistical power ($1-\beta$) was projected at 80%. As a result of these calculations, the minimum required sample size was determined to be 52 participants. Considering potential data loss and incomplete responses, %20 increase was planned; therefore, the target was set to include at least 63 participants.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with the IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 29.0. IBM Corp. Armonk, New York, USA. The suitability of the numerical variables for normal distribution was examined using skewness and kurtosis values. Skewness and kurtosis values within the range of -1.5 to +1.5 were considered indicative of a normal distribution¹¹. Variables with normal distribution are expressed as mean±standart deviation (mean±SD); variables without normal distribution are expressed as median (minimum (min)-maximum (max)); and categorical variables are expressed as number (n) and percent (%). The telehealth knowledge, awareness, readiness, and professional anxiety variables in the groups were compared with the independent samples-t-test, and correlations among variables were assessed using Pearson's correlation analysis. According to studies in the health-sciences literature, correlation coefficients were interpreted using the following cut-points (by absolute value): 0.00–0.19 very weak, 0.20–0.39 weak,

0.40–0.69 moderate, 0.70–0.89 strong, and 0.90–1.00 very strong^{12,13}. The statistical significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

FINDINGS

A total of 121 students participated (121/180,-response rate: 67.2%, median age: 20 years; range: 18–40). Most participants were female (n=90, 74.4%), and 31 were male (25.6%). Participants were enrolled in Anesthesia (n=37, 30.6%), Emergency and First Aid (n=5, 4.1%), Elderly Care (n=65, 53.7%), or other departments (n=14, 11.6%). Thirty-eight students (31.4%) were in their first year and 83 (68.6%) were in their second year. Prior awareness of telehealth was reported by 50 students (41.3%), while 71 (58.7%) had not heard of it. Forty-one students (33.9%) had previously received care via telehealth, whereas 80 (66.1%) had not (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participants.

Characteristics	Total (n=121)
Age (years)median (min-max)	20.00 (18-40)
Gender(n,%)	
Female	90 (74.4%)
Male	31 (25.6%)
Department(yes,n,%)	
Anesthesia	37 (30.6%)
Emergency and First Aid	5 (4.1%)
Elderly Care	65 (53.7%)
Others	14 (11.6%)
Current class year	
First	38 (31.4%)
Second	83 (68.6%)
Have you heard of telehealth before?	
Yes	50 (41.3%)
No	71 (58.7%)
Have you ever received care via telehealth?	
Yes	41 (33.9%)
No	80 (66.1%)

n: number, *min*: minimum, *max*: maximum, %: percent.

In the intergroup comparison, second-year students scored higher than first-year students on the technological subdimension of telehealth readiness (27.32 ± 6.27 vs. 24.68 ± 8.33 , $p = 0.016$) and on overall telehealth readiness (93.79 ± 21.81 vs. 85.92 ± 27.23 , $p = 0.042$). They also reported higher occupational health-related anxiety (11.22 ± 3.39 vs. 9.63 ± 2.89 , $p = 0.022$). However, no between-year differences were observed for the other variables ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Differences in Telehealth Knowledge, Awareness, Readiness, and Professional Anxiety Across Class Year

Characteristics	Total (n=121) X±SD	First year (n=38) X±SD	Second year (n=83) X±SD	p	t
Telehealth Knowledge/Awareness					
Knowledge Level	25.25±9.92	58.94 ±14.10	66.74 ±16.87	0.937	-0.704
Awareness Level	24.09±7.73	24.31 ±10.37	25.68 ±9.73	0.163	-1.384
Attitudes	28.42±9.36	26.68 ±10.35	29.22 ±8.82	0.112	-1.393
Total	77.77±23.84	73.65 ±26.88	79.66 ±22.23	0.171	-1.289
Telehealth Readiness					
Cognitive	25.05±6.94	23.84±8.01	25.61±6.36	0.175	-1.307
Technological	26.49±7.06	24.68±8.33	27.32±6.27	0.016*	-1.931
Affective	18.17±5.39	17.21±5.94	18.61±5.09	0.168	-1.334
Implementation	21.59±6.24	20.18±7.12	22.24±5.72	0.056	-1.695
Total	91.32±23.81	85.92±27.23	93.79 ±21.81	0.042*	-1.701
Vocational Anxiety Scale					
Professional knowledge	23.51±7.11	21.55 ±6.42	24.40 ±7.26	0.346	-2.079
Working life	18.47±5.57	17.36±5.35	18.97±5.62	0.411	-1.480
Occupational health	10.72±3.31	9.63±2.89	11.22±3.39	0.022*	-2.513
Communication skills	11.58±4.24	10.39±3.57	12.13±4.43	0.078	-2.118
Total	64.29±16.40	58.94±14.10	66.74 ±16.87	0.059	-2.479

n=number, X: mean, SD: standart deviation, Independent sample t-test, * $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Correlations among Telehealth Knowledge, Awareness, Readiness, and Professional Anxiety.

Characteristics (n=121)		Vocational Anxiety Scale				
		Professional knowledge	Working life	Occupational health	Communication skills	Total
Telehealth Knowledge/Awareness						
Knowledge Level	p	0.561	0.379	0.154	0.097	0.107
	r	0.053	0.081	0.091	0.289	0.243
Awareness Level	p	0.182	0.374	0.198	0.999	0.254
	r	0.122	0.082	0.118	0.000	0.104
Attitudes	p	0.138	0.475	0.138	0.965	0.232
	r	0.136	0.066	0.136	0.004	0.109
Total	p	0.209	0.350	0.647	0.121	0.185
	r	0.115	0.086	0.042	0.746	0.121
Telehealth Readiness						
Cognitive	p	0.423	0.037*	0.008*	0.275	0.156
	r	-0.073	-0.190	-0.239	-0.100	0.234
Technological	p	0.237	<0.001*	0.002*	0.171	0.014*
	r	0.066	-0.286	-0.259	0.087	-0.201
Affective	p	0.458	0.074	0.011*	0.299	0.156
	r	-0.068	0.163	-0.229	-0.095	0.088
Implementation	p	0.163	0.010*	0.003*	0.103	0.200
	r	0.090	-0.210	-0.245	0.131	0.186
Total	p	0.384	0.010*	0.004	0.259	0.034*
	r	0.080	-0.232	-0.263	-0.103	-0.193

n=number, Pearson correlation, * $p < 0.05$.

Telehealth readiness was negatively correlated with several domains of vocational anxiety. Cognitive readiness showed a very weak correlation with working life ($r = 0.190$, $p = 0.037$) and a weak correlation with occupational health ($r = -0.239$, $p = 0.008$). Technological readiness demonstrated a weak correlation with working life ($r = -0.286$, $p < 0.001$), occupational health ($r = -0.259$, $p = 0.002$), and total anxiety ($r = -0.201$, $p = 0.014$). Affective readiness had a weak correlation with occupational health ($r = -0.229$, $p = 0.011$). Implementation readiness was weakly correlated with both working life ($r = -0.210$, $p = 0.010$) and occupational health ($r = -0.245$, $p = 0.003$). Finally, total telehealth readiness showed weak correlations with working life ($r = -0.232$, $p = 0.010$), occupational health ($r = -0.263$, $p = 0.004$), and total anxiety ($r = -0.193$, $p = 0.034$; weak). However, no significant correlations were found between the telehealth knowledge/awareness, the other subdomains of telehealth readiness, and vocational anxiety scale, (all $p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

In the current study, second-year students demonstrated higher technological readiness, overall telehealth readiness, and occupational health-related anxiety compared to first-year students. Moreover, as telehealth readiness increased, several domains of vocational anxiety, particularly working life and occupational health, decreased, although the strength of these inverse relationships ranged from very weak to weak. To our knowledge, this study is one of the first to compare and examine the relationship between the level of telehealth knowledge, awareness, readiness, and professional anxiety among health services vocational school students.

Telehealth is considered a routine and essential component of health care delivery, valued for improving access and convenience and for maintaining continuity of care during public health emergencies¹⁴. Therefore, it is crucial that all students and professionals in the health sciences develop sufficient knowledge and awareness of telehealth and do not experience unnecessary professional anxiety regarding its use. Although studies investigating telehealth knowledge and awareness have been conducted among medical students, health sciences students, and various healthcare professionals in the literature^{7,15,16}, data on telehealth knowledge and awareness among healthcare services students in Türkiye

remain limited. Compared to second-year students, our findings showed that first-year health services vocational school students demonstrated lower technological readiness, total telehealth readiness, and occupational health-related anxiety. In the early stage of training, they have had fewer opportunities to practice with health technologies and less awareness of potential occupational health risks, which naturally leads to lower readiness scores and less concern about work-related health issues. Since telehealth has not yet been fully integrated into vocational school curricula, both year levels receive only basic theoretical knowledge, which results in comparable levels of understanding and awareness. Taken together, these results indicate that while progression through training may increase students' confidence and readiness in technology-related domains, the absence of systematic telehealth instruction prevents substantial gains in knowledge and awareness, leading to similar levels across cohorts. Additionally, vocational anxiety is often influenced by broader issues such as job prospects, professional identity, or workload expectations, which tend to be shared across all students regardless of their year level. This may account for why both groups reported similar levels of anxiety, except in certain subdomains (e.g., occupational health) where second-year students' approaching graduation might make them slightly more concerned.

Previous research has shown that telehealth knowledge and awareness among health sciences students are often limited, and this lack of familiarity may contribute to uncertainty and professional anxiety^{7,16}. While telehealth education is increasingly emphasized, many programs still do not provide structured courses or practical exposure, leaving students with only a general understanding. Professional anxiety in turn is shaped by multiple factors, including career expectations, workload, and perceived competence, and may not be strongly influenced by digital health alone⁹. In line with these observations, our study found that higher telehealth readiness was weakly but consistently associated with lower vocational anxiety across domains. However, our measure of professional anxiety captured general career concerns, which may not align closely with specific telehealth attitudes. Thus, their professional anxieties tend to focus on broader issues (job security, clinical skills, workload) rather than on technology per se.

The strengths of our study include the participation of students from different provinces and universities in Türkiye, which increases the generalizability of the findings, as well as the use of a professional anxiety scale specifically designed for health services vocational school students. Nonetheless, several limitations should be acknowledged. Because the survey was administered online, we were unable to obtain responses from all eligible students and thus could not reach a larger sample size, which may limit the precision and generalizability of the estimates. The cross-sectional, self-reported design precludes causal inferences and may be subject to response bias. We measured only correlations at one point in time; unmeasured factors (such as personality traits or prior technology training) could influence both readiness and anxiety. Moreover, the vocational anxiety scale was generic and may not capture anxieties specific to emerging technologies. Given the limitations of this study, future studies should recruit larger, multi-center samples to improve precision and generalizability. Longitudinal designs are needed to track changes in readiness and anxiety over time and to support causal inferences. Combining self-report with objective assessments (e.g., digital literacy/skills tests) and using telehealth-specific anxiety measures will reduce bias and better capture technology-related concerns. Additionally, incorporating potential moderators (e.g., prior technology training, personality, clinical exposure) can clarify what drives variability in students' readiness and anxiety.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights that while second-year students demonstrated higher technological and overall telehealth readiness and greater occupational health-related anxiety, overall telehealth knowledge and awareness remained similar across class years, reflecting the limited integration of telehealth education into current curricula. In light of these results, it is emphasized that future healthcare professionals should receive training on telehealth during their undergraduate education. Curricular integration of telehealth appears insufficient despite students' high interest.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no relevant financial or non-financial interests.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by MTY, EU, Serife Seyma Yaylacı, B. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Mustafa Tanık Yıldız and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Ethics approval

The the Non-Drug and Medical Device Research Ethics Committee of KTO Karatay University with the numbered 2025/016 approved the present study and all subjects gave written informed consent based on the principles set out in the Helsinki Declaration.

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